

Artificial Intelligence and the Transformation of Online Search: Findings from a Study Commissioned by the German State Media Authorities

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1. Introduction

This study investigates how the integration of generative artificial intelligence (Gen AI) in online search transforms search engine functionality and what implications these changes have for content monetization and the diversity of online information. The research addresses two core questions: (1) Does the integration of Gen AI represent a radical departure from traditional search engine evolution or merely an incremental development? and (2) How might AI-driven search affect the economic models of content providers and, consequently, the diversity of information available on the web?

The investigation is structured into two distinct parts. Part 1 focuses on a comprehensive functional analysis of current AI-enhanced search systems. This analysis is carried out on several dimensions. At the technical level, the study evaluates the underlying algorithms and the interplay between implicit knowledge bases—derived from pre-trained language models—and explicit document indexes, as highlighted by Tonello (2024). On the presentation level, the research examines how AI-generated answers are displayed on search engine results pages (SERPs), assessing factors such as factual accuracy, the occurrence of hallucinations, and the frequency and clarity of source attribution. On the interaction level, the study compares user-system dynamics, particularly analyzing whether search queries are resolved directly within the AI system or whether users are directed to external content. The methodological approach is based on a literature review—including scientific research, journalistic accounts, and practitioner literature. The literature review spans disciplines such as computer science, information science, communication studies, and psychology, ensuring an interdisciplinary perspective on the topic. Furthermore, empirical tests using standardized prompts across various systems such as Google AI Overviews, Bing Chat, and Perplexity AI are conducted.

Part 2 delves into the economic effects and diversity risks associated with the integration of Gen AI in search engines. The primary hypothesis is that AI-generated summaries on SERPs lead to a significant reduction in clicks, thereby decreasing the web traffic that content providers rely on for monetization through advertising or subscriptions. This potential decline in traffic could undermine the financial viability of content creators, particularly smaller providers, and may result in a market where larger, well-resourced entities dominate the visibility landscape. The study also explores how such shifts might affect the broader information and opinion diversity on the internet. Drawing on earlier work on source distribution and result overlap (Yagci et al., 2022; Norocel & Lewandowski, 2023) as well as theoretical frameworks on algorithmic bias (Introna & Nissenbaum, 2000; Baeza-Yates, 2018), the research critically assesses whether Gen-AI systems might structurally disadvantage smaller content providers by preferentially featuring larger or more established sources.

The outcomes of this study provide nuanced insights into the dual nature of Gen AI in online search. On one hand, AI can enhance search efficiency and improve user experience through more direct query resolution; on the other, it poses significant risks for the traditional monetization models of online content, which may ultimately affect the production and diversity of information. By rigorously analyzing both the technological and economic dimensions of Gen AI integration, this study aims to

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inform policymakers, industry stakeholders, and academic researchers about the benefits and challenges associated with the adoption of Gen AI in search engines.

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